
Relationship Between Distributed Leadership in Government Secondary School and Organizational Disinvestment of Teachers

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Abstract:

Since the outbreak of the Covid-19 health crisis, the education system around the world has experienced a crisis on several levels, notwithstanding the many efforts made to this end. This study is aimed at studying the relationship between distributed leadership in Government secondary school and Organizational Disinvestment of teachers. Data were collected from 225 teachers from public secondary schools in Cameroon aged between 24 and 63 years old (Mean = 41; SD = 8.84); from a composite questionnaire containing scales of turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6; Bothma & Roodt, 2013), Workplace Counterproductivity Scale (WCS; Marcus et al., 2002), Counterproductive Work Behavior Scale (CWBS; Gruys & Sackett, 2003). The TIS-6 is a 6-item self-report questionnaire assessing turnover intention (the intention to leave or stay) and the Distributed Leadership Inventory (DLI; Hulpia et al., 2009). A correlation and regression were performed. The results show that the presence of distributed leadership is associated with a low degree of organizational disinvestment among teachers $r(223) = -.221, p < .01, F(1,223) = 9.59, p < .01$). The theoretical and practical implications of these results were discussed.

Keywords: Distributed Leadership, Government secondary school, Organizational Disinvestment, Teachers

Introduction

Since the advent of Covid-19, many high schools have been faced with major challenges: rising pedagogical demands, scarcity of human and material resources, and growing pressure for results. In the face of these challenges, distributed leadership (Spillane, 2006) offers a promising response, by proposing a sharing of responsibilities between management, teachers and administrative staff. This model aims to strengthen collective commitment and improve pedagogical quality. However, this redistribution of leadership does not always go hand in hand with an increase in teachers' organizational commitment; in some cases, it leads instead to organizational disinvestment, particularly when roles are unclear or the workload excessive. This sharing of responsibilities can also lead to organizational disinvestment, particularly when teachers perceive an overload, a lack of clarity about their roles or a rigid bureaucratic environment (teachersnotes.net). Several studies highlight these paradoxical effects: for example, Thien (2019) identifies bureaucratic structures as a brake on distributed leadership, potentially diminishing teachers' affective engagement (Thien, 2019). In addition, teachers may experience a form of "distributed pain" - a feeling of extra work without adequate support - which affects their professional well-being (Tian et al., 2021). This dual reality calls into question the underlying mechanisms linking distributed leadership and organizational disinvestment. On the one hand, the literature shows positive effects on teacher satisfaction and motivation in a distributed context (Ma & Marion, 2025; Hulpia et al., 2010). On the other hand, studies highlight limitations linked to workload, rigid governance or lack of resources (Tian et al., 2021; TeachersNotes, 2025).

For example, in a study of a sample of 1,522 teachers in Belgium, Hulpia et al. (2012) showed that cooperation within the management team and the quality of support are more important determinants of organizational commitment than the mere distribution of functions. The work of Tian et al (2021) underlines that pyramidal structures intensify hierarchical distance and hinder teacher empowerment. Furthermore, Ma & Marion (2025), in a study in China, confirm that distributed leadership improves job satisfaction, provided teachers perceive genuine role clarification and institutional support. Barros Gavilanes (2017) highlighted that teachers are more committed when decision-making is genuinely participative and perceived as fair; conversely, the absence of feedback or overload leads to professional disinvestment.

This work highlights the conditions necessary for the positive impact of distributed leadership: support, cooperation, clarity, structured feedback. They form the theoretical basis of our research and shed light on possible specificities in the Cameroonian context. Studying the relationship between distributed leadership and teachers' organizational disinvestment in Cameroonian high schools therefore appears interesting, for two reasons. Firstly, although distributed leadership is valued, the reality in Cameroon-with inadequate training, rigid bureaucracy and disparities between urban and rural areas-could transform this strategy into a factor of stress and disengagement. Secondly, from an academic point of view, this study is in line with research on organizational commitment, often carried out in European or Asian contexts, but little addressed in sub-Saharan Africa. Thus, our research aims to shed light on: (a) the mechanisms linking distributed leadership and teacher disinvestment; (b) how this link manifests itself in Cameroonian high schools; and (c) under what structural or contextual conditions (support, role clarity) distributed leadership can strengthen rather than weaken institutional commitment. These questions are intended to enrich the international literature and propose pragmatic solutions for the Cameroonian context. This study thus aims to map

the interactions between distributed leadership and faculty commitment in Cameroonian high schools. The stakes here are twofold: theoretical (refining the understanding of distributed leadership in developed contexts) and practical (formulating recommendations adapted to Cameroonian realities).

METHOD

Participants and Procedure

This study applied a cross-sectional design with a convenience sampling. The sample consisted of 225 teachers from public secondary schools in Cameroon aged between 24 and 63 years old (Mean = 41; SD = 8.84). Many of them were female teachers (56.9%). The teaching experience of participants was ranged from 1 to 30 years old (Mean = 13.9; SD = 6.56). Regarding the number of public secondary schools where they had practiced, 80 had already taught in 1 public secondary school (35.6%), 89 in 2 public secondary schools (39.6%), 46 in 3 public secondary schools (20.4%), and 10 in 4 public secondary schools (4.4%). Data was collected from June to November 2022. Before completing the questionnaire, each participant signed a consent form highlighting the research purpose and warranting the anonymous and confidential nature of the study. All the participants did not hold any administrative position neither in the school nor in the government body.

Measures

Organizational Disinvestment

The organizational disinvestment in the participants was measured through three different scales: Turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6; Bothma & Roodt, 2013), Workplace Counterproductivity Scale (WCS; Marcus et al., 2002), and Counterproductive Work Behavior Scale (CWBS; Gruys & Sackett, 2003). The TIS-6 is a 6-item self-report questionnaire assessing turnover intention (the intention to leave or stay). Each item was rated on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (always). The WCS is a self-report questionnaire measuring many workplace counterproductive behaviors. It was used to assess aggressive (12 items) and stealing (5 items) behaviors. For each of all the 17 items, participants rated the frequency with which the prohibited act was executed during the last twelve month on a 7-point Likert scale: 0 (never), 1 (once), 2 (two or three times), 3 (several times), 4 (often), 5 (very often), 6 (every time). The CWBS is also a self-report to capture counterproductive behaviors, which was used to assess Misuse of Information (5 items), Misuse of Time and Resources (13 items), Poor Attendance (5 items), and Poor Quality Work (3 items). Participants were asked to rate whether they would engage in each of the counterproductive behaviors on a seven-point scale ranging from 1 (no matter what the circumstances, i would not engage in the behavior) to 7 (in a wide variety of circumstances, i would engage in the behavior).

Distributed Leadership

The distributed leadership was measured with the Distributed Leadership Inventory (DLI; Hulpia et al., 2009). The DLI is a 29-item self-report questionnaire assessing the four factors of Distributed Leadership: cooperation of the leadership team (10 items), participative decision making (6 items), support leadership (10 items), and supervision leadership (3 items). The participants were invited to rate their perception of the cooperation of the leadership team, of the extent to which school members can participate in school decision-making, and of the individual supportive and supervisory leadership functions of the principal, the assistant principals, and the teacher leaders on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

Difficulties

To collect the data for this study, we faced several difficulties: finding schools that agreed to make their teachers, especially second-cycle exam classes, available to us, disorder among some teachers, non-compliance with instructions, break times and the time allocated to filling in the questionnaire.

Ethical considerations

All participants were informed of the study's objective, the confidential and voluntary nature of their participation, as well as the possibility of withdrawing from the study at any time. Subsequently, they were given an informed consent form that they had to read and sign if they approved of the study.

Data analysis

Data were processed with jamovi-2.5.3.0 software in two steps. The first step was the estimation of descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and correlation coefficients between study variables. The correlation analysis showed the significant links between distributed leadership and organizational disinvestment variables, which allowed to perform regression analysis. The second step was simple and multiple linear regression analyses. In the statistical model, distributed leadership factors were introduced as predictors. The simple linear regression tested the relationships between distributed leadership and organizational disinvestment variables identified as significant in the correlation matrix. Multiple linear regression tested the best predictor for turnover intention, poor attendance, and poor work quality. The enter method was used by including the predictors into analysis at the same time.

Results

Measurement tools

Reliability analysis

Reliability score of Distributed leadership

The score of Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's Omega for the turn Cooperation of the leadership team over dimension are .829 and .830, respectively. For the participative decision making dimension, the scores of .740 and .756 are recorded. The theft Leadership support dimension has scores of .924 and .925. As for the misuse of info Leadership supervision dimension, we record .837 and .851. All these values show that these dimensions have good internal consistency.

Reliability score of organizational disinvestment

The results show that shows that Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's Omega for the turnover dimension are .782 and .795, respectively. For the aggression dimension, the scores of .926 and .969 are recorded. The theft dimension has scores of .922 and .934. As for the misuse of information dimension, we record .891 and .913. The misuse of time and resources dimension records scores of .867 and .918. The poor attendance dimension records scores of .592 and .741. Finally, the poor work quality dimension records scores of .336 and .499. All these values show that these dimensions have good internal consistency. However, the dimensions poor attendance and poor work quality do not have good internal consistency.

Secondary factors are factors about which assumptions have not been made, but which may have effects on distributed leadership and organizational disinvestment. These are also label variables or socio-demographic variables: sex, marital status, age, number of children, number of schools and professional experience. We examined their relationship with distributed leadership and organizational disinvestment respectively.

Gender

Results breaks down the participants according to their gender and shows that 97 men (45.6%) participated in the study compared to 128 women (54.4%). This makes a total of 225 participants. These data show that the participants in this study are predominantly women compared to men. However, they do not allow us to conclude that gender has an effect on organizational disinvestment. To do this, we will use the inference test to check if these differences are significantly different.

Comparison of the degree of organizational disinvestment of men and women showed significant effect of gender on the Wilks' Lambda = .87, $F(7,217) = 4.68$, $p < .01$. Specifically, there is an effect of gender on three dimensions of organizational disinvestment. Women ($M = 3,996$) have a higher turnover score than men ($M = 3,689$) $F(7,217) = 9.35$, $p < .01$; indicating that they no longer intend to leave their teaching jobs. They ($M = 2.143$) also have the highest score on poor work quality $F(7,217) = 7.02$, $p < .01$. That is, compared to men, they intentionally do their job less well. On the other hand, on aggression, it is men ($M = 0.873$) who record the highest score $F(7,217) = 5.61$, $p < .01$. They are therefore the ones who, among other things, insult colleagues more in the workplace. Results also showed an overall effect of sex on distributed leadership Wilks' Lambda = .93, $F(4,220) = 4.22$, $p < .01$. Specifically, men score higher than women on Cooperation of Leadership Team $F(4,220) = 4.44$, $p < .05$, Participative Decision Making $F(4,220) = 10.38$, $p < .01$, Leadership Support $F(4,220) = 11.35$, $p < .01$. In other words, compared to women, men perceive more cooperation within the management team, participate more in decision-making and feel more supported by the school's management team.

Marital status

The results break down the participants according to their marital status and show that 110 (48.9%) of them are married, 51 (22.7%) of them are single, 30 (13.3%) are divorced and 34 (15.1%) are in single relationship. This makes a total of 225 participants. These data show that the participants in this study are predominantly married. However, they do not allow us to conclude that marital status has an effect on organizational disinvestment. To do this, we will use the inference test to check if these differences are significantly different.

Marital status has a significant effect on organizational disinvestment Wilks' Lambda = .72, $F(21,618) = 3.62$, $p < .001$. More precisely (table ****), the bride and groom have the highest score on aggression $F(21,618) = 3.31$, $p < .05$, misuse of resources, $F(21,618) = 5.98$, $p < .001$ and poor attendance at work $F(21,618) = 2.62$, $p < .001$. The bride and groom are therefore the ones who most assault their colleague or students, who intentionally use the resources of the school more badly and who are the most absenteeists. On the other hand, for poor quality of work, divorced women have the highest score, $F(21,618) = 3.01$, $p < .05$. For the other dimensions, the results are non-significant. The results also showed an effect of marital status on distributed leadership, particularly on the supervision leadership dimension where teachers in a simple romantic relationship had the highest score $F(12,577) = 3.89$, $p < .05$.

.05. They are the ones who perceive more that the management team follows the evolution of their professional activities within the school.

Age

The results shows that age is not correlated with the different dimensions of organizational disinvestment: turnover $r(225) = .09, p > .05$; Aggression $r(225) = .06, p > .05$; Theft $r(120) = -.01, p > .05$; Information Misuse $r(225) = -.01, p > .05$; Resources Misuse $r(225) = .08, p > .05$; Poor attendance $r(225) = .09, p > .05$ and Poor work Quality $r(225) = .09, p > .05$. Age is therefore not related to the behaviours characterizing organizational disinvestment. In terms of the relationship between age and distributed leadership (Table ****), only one correlation was significant. The one that links age with leadership support $r(225) = -.16, p < .01$. This is a negative correlation, i.e. the older the teacher, the less the teacher perceives the support of the management team and vice versa. Correlations with other dimensions of leadership are non-significant.

Number of children

The results shows that the number of children is positively correlated with four dimensions of organizational disinvestment: Aggression $r(225) = .20, p < .01$; Misuse Information $r(225) = .20, p < .01$; Resources Misuse $r(225) = .29, p < .01$ and Poor attendance $r(225) = .17, p < .01$. Those who have more children are those who are absenteeists, aggressive in the workplace, intentionally and prohibitively use high school information and resources. Correlations with other dimensions are non-significant. Regarding the relationship between the number of children and distributed leadership, only one correlation was significant. The one that links the number of children with leadership support $r(225) = -.16, p < .01$. This correlation is negative, that is, the more children you have, the less you perceive the support of the management team and vice versa. Correlations with other dimensions of leadership are non-significant.

Number of schools

It appears that the number of schools in which the teacher taught is positively correlated with two dimensions of organizational disinvestment: Aggression $r(225) = .13, p < .05$ and Resources Misuse $r(225) = .23, p < .01$. Those teachers who have worked in more high schools, are the most aggressive in the workplace and intentionally and in a prohibited manner use the resources of the school. Correlations with other dimensions are non-significant. Regarding the relationship between the number of schools and distributed leadership, only one correlation was significant. The one that links the number of schools with leadership support $r(225) = -.18, p < .05$. This correlation is negative, that is to say the more one has exercised in several high schools, the less one perceives the support of the management team and vice versa. Correlations with other dimensions of leadership are non-significant.

Professional experience

The results shows that work experience has significant correlations with four dimensions of organizational disinvestment. More specifically, it is positively correlated with turnover $r(225) = .27, p < .01$ and poor work quality $r(225) = .15, p < .05$. Teachers who have more professional experience are those who are more intent on changing professions and are

deliberately doing their job poorly. Work experience is this time negatively correlated with Information Misuse $r(225) = -.14, p < .05$ and theft $r(225) = -.15, p < .05$. This indicates that those with less work experience intentionally misuse high school information and indulge more in flying behavior in the workplace. Correlations with other dimensions are non-significant. The relationship between work experience and distributed leadership, shows only one significant correlation. The relationship between professional experience with leadership support $r(225) = -.18, p < .05$. This correlation is negative, i.e. the more professional experience increases, the less support from the management team is perceived and vice versa. Correlations with other dimensions of leadership are non-significant.

Overall, the analysis of secondary factors showed that all six sociodemographic variables are related to the two main variables in the study. The exception of age may be noted, which showed no significant link with organizational disinvestment. It is now relevant to analyze the main factors in order to be able to decide on the assumptions.

Cooperation of leadership team and organizational disinvestment

Analysis of tables 1, 2, and 3 show that participants scored low to high on different dimensions of organizational disinvestment. Specifically, they scored high Turnover ($M = 3.86$; $SD = 0.76$). This means that statistically, they very often consider leaving their job as high school teachers. They obtained also low scores on Aggression ($M = 0.72$; $SD = 0.84$), Theft ($M = 0.81$; $SD = 0.70$), Misuse of information ($M = 1.35$; $SD = 0.88$) and Misuse of resources ($M = 1.85$; $SD = 0.77$). Statistically, participants rarely engage in aggressive and/or flying behaviors during work. The same applies to the inappropriate use of information or work material. Concerning Poor attendance ($M = 3.86$; $SD = 0.76$) and Poor work quality ($M = 3.86$; $SD = 0.76$), they obtained fair scores, which means they are often late at workplace and/or often do poor quality work.

Table 1: *Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix between cooperation of leadership team and organizational disinvestment*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Turnover	3.86	0.76	---							
2. Aggression	0.72	0.84	-.147*	---						
3. Theft	0.81	0.70	-.316**	.859*	---					
4. Information Misuse	1.35	0.88	-.224**	.764*	.786*	---				
5. Resources Misuse	1.85	0.77	-.002	.802*	.769*	.805*	---			
6. Poor attendance	2.01	0.67	.245**	.501*	.391*	.438*	.561*	---		
7. Poor work quality	2.02	0.81	.325**	.358*	.293*	.259*	.469*	.567**	---	
8. Cooperation of LT	2.46	0.46	-.203**	.058	.172*	.072	.025	-.221**	-.115	--

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$; LT = Leadership Team

The table 1 shows that participants achieved an average score of Leadership Cooperation ($M = 2.46$; $SD = 0.46$). They therefore perceive a certain cooperation between the members of the management team of their high school. It is also apparent from the table that there is a negative correlation between Cooperation of Leadership Team and: Turnover

intention $r(223) = -.203, p < .01$ and Poor attendance $r(223) = -.221, p < .01$. But a positive correlation between Cooperation of Leadership Team and Theft $r(223) = .172, p < .05$. These results mean that, those who do not perceive cooperation between members of the high school leadership team are who are not only considering leaving their jobs as high school teachers, but also those who are most absentee. Paradoxically, those who perceive cooperation within the management team are those who adopt work-related flying behaviors. Correlations with other dimensions of organizational disinvestment are not significant.

Table 2

Simple linear regression between cooperation of leadership team and organizational disinvestment

Dependant variables	Estimate (β)	T	R	R ²	Adjuted R ²	F
Turnover	-.338	-3.10**	.203	.041	.037	9.59**
Theft	.264	2.61**	.172	.030	.025	6.79**
Poor attendance	-.323	-3.38**	.221	.049	.044	11.4**

Note. Predictor = Cooperation of Leadership Team

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

The table 2 confirms the significant correlations obtained above. It shows that Cooperation of Leadership Team predicts Turnover intention $F(1,223) = 9.59, p < .01$, Theft $F(1,223) = 9.59, p < .01$ and Poor attendance $F(1,223) = 9.59, p < .01$; by explaining respectively 3.7%, 2.5% and 4.4% of the variance of each of these dimensions of organizational disinvestment. This implies that a degree increase in the cooperation of the management team is reduced: Turnover intention of 33.8% ($\beta = -.338, t(223) = -3.10, p < .01$) and Poor attendance of 32.3% ($\beta = -.323, t(223) = -3.38, p < .01$). On the other hand, it increases Theft by 26.4% ($\beta = .264, t(223) = 2.64, p < .01$). The degree of perception of cooperation within the management team is therefore related to the degree of Turnover intention, theft and poor attendance among the participants.

2.2. Participative decision making and organizational disinvestment

The table shows that participants scored an average Participatory Decision Making score ($M = 2.55; SD = 0.49$). They therefore often feel involved in decision-making in their high school. On the relationship between Participative Decision Making and Organizational Disinvestment, the table ... show that there is a negative correlation between Participative Decision Making and: Turnover intention $r(223) = -.171, p < .05$; Misuse of resources $r(223) = -.140, p < .05$; Poor attendance $r(223) = -.190, p < .01$ and Poor work quality $r(223) = -.145, p < .05$. These results mean that teachers who do not feel involved in decision-making within their high school are those who: plan to quit their job as a high school teacher, use work materials inappropriately, are the most absenteeists and are the least effective at work. Correlations with other dimensions of organizational disinvestment are not significant.

Table 3
 Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix between Participative decision making and organizational disinvestment

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Turnover	3.86	0.76	---							
2. Aggression	0.72	0.84	-.147*	---						
3. Theft	0.81	0.70	-.316**	.859**	---					
4. Information Misuse	1.35	0.88	-.224**	.764**	.786**	---				
5. Resources Misuse	1.85	0.77	-.002	.802**	.769**	.805**	---			
6. Poor attendance	2.01	0.67	.245**	.501**	.391**	.438**	.561**	---		
7. Poor work quality	2.02	0.81	.325**	.358**	.293**	.259**	.469**	.567**	---	
8. Participative DM	2.55	0.49	-.171*	-.032	-.039	-.063	-.140*	-.190**	-.145*	--

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$; DM = Decision Making

The table 3 shows that Participative Decision Making predicts several organizational disinvestment dimensions, namely: Turnover intention $F(1,223) = 6.75, p < .01$; Misuse of resources $F(1,223) = 4.46, p < .01$; Poor attendance $8.39, p < .01$ and Poor work $F(1,223) = 4.81, p < .05$. Participative Decision Making explains respectively 3%, 2%, 3.6% and 2.1% each of those Organizational Disinvestment dimensions. A one-degree increase on Participatory Decision Making reduced: Turnover intention of 26.4% ($\beta = -.264, t(223) = -2.60, p < .01$), Misuse of resources 21.9% ($\beta = -.219, t(223) = -2.11, p < .05$); Poor attendance 25.9% ($\beta = -.259, t(223) = -2.90, p < .01$) and Poor Work Quality 23.8% ($\beta = -.238, t(223) = -2.19, p < .01$).

Table 4
 Simple linear regression between Participative decision making and organizational disinvestment

Dependant variables	Estimate (β)	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	Adjuted <i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>
Turnover	-.264	-2.60**	.171	.030	.025	6.75**
Ressources Misuse	-.219	-2.11*	.140	.020	.015	4.46**
Poor attendance	-.259	-2.90**	.190	.036	.032	8.39**
Poor work quality	-.238	-2.19*	.145	.021	.017	4.81*

Note. Predictor = Participative decision making
 * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

The table 4 confirms the significant correlations obtained above. It shows that Participative decision making predicts Turnover intention $F(1,233) = 6.75, p < .01$, Ressources Misuse $F(1,233) = 4.46, p < .01$, Poor Attendance $F(1,233) = 8.39, p < .01$ and Poor Work Quality $F(1,233) = 4.81, p < .05$; by explaining respectively 1.71%, 1.40% 1.9% and 1.45% of the variance of each of these dimensions of organizational disinvestment. This implies that a degree increase on Participative decision making reduced: Turnover intention of 26.4% ($\beta = -.260, t(233) = -4.35, p < .01$), Ressources Misuse 21.9% ($\beta = -.211, t(233) = -2.65, p < .01$), Poor attendance of 25.9% ($\beta = -.290, t(223) = -2.65, p < .01$) and Poor Work Quality 23.8% ($\beta = -.238, t(233) = -2.19, p < .05$). The degree of perception of the support

received from the management team is therefore related to the degree of Turnover intention, Poor attendance and Poor Work Quality among participants.

Leadership Support and organizational disinvestment

Table 5

Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix between Leadership Support and organizational disinvestment

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Turnover	3.86	0.76	---							
2. Aggression	0.72	0.84	-.147*	---						
3. Theft	0.81	0.70	-.316**	.859*	---					
4. Information Misuse	1.35	0.88	-.224**	.764*	.786*	---				
5. Resources Misuse	1.85	0.77	-.002	.802*	.769*	.805*	---			
6. Poor attendance	2.01	0.67	.245**	.501*	.391*	.438*	.561**	---		
7. Poor work quality	2.02	0.81	.325**	.358*	.293*	.259*	.469**	.567**	---	
8. Leadership Support	2.33	0.59	-.280*	.005	.079	-.023	-.106	-.175**	-.174**	--

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

The table 5 shows that participants achieved an average Leadership Support score ($M = 2.33$; $SD = 0.59$). As a result, they perceive some support from members of their high school's management team. It is also apparent from the table ... that there is a negative correlation between Leadership Support and: Turnover intention $r(223) = -.280$, $p < .05$; Poor attendance $r(223) = -.175$, $p < .01$ and Poor Work Quality $r(223) = -.174$, $p < .01$. These results mean that, those who do not perceive support from members of the high school leadership team are who are not only considering quitting their high school teacher jobs, but also those who are the most absentee and least effective at work. Correlations with other dimensions of organizational disinvestment are not significant.

Table 6

Simple linear regression between Leadership Support and organizational disinvestment

Dependant variables	Estimate (β)	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>	R^2	Adjuted R^2	<i>F</i>
Turnover	-.359	-4.35**	.280	.078	.074	18.9**
Poor attendance	-.197	-2.65**	.175	.031	.026	7.01**
Poor workquality	-.237	-2.64*	.174	.030	.026	6.95**

Note. Predictor = Leadership Support

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

The table 6 confirms the significant correlations obtained above. It shows that Leadership Support predicts Turnover intention $F(1,223) = 18.9$, $p < .01$, Poor Attendance $F(1,223) = 7.01$, $p < .01$ and Poor Work Quality $F(1,223) = 6.95$, $p < .01$; by explaining respectively 2.8%, 1.75% and 1.74% of the variance of each of these dimensions of organizational disinvestment. This implies that a degree increase on Leadership Support reduced: Turnover intention of 35.9% ($\beta = -.359$, $t(223) = -4.35$, $p < .01$), Poor attendance of

19.7% ($\beta = -.197$, $t(223) = -2.65$, $p < .01$) and Poor Work Quality 23.7% ($\beta = -.237$, $t(223) = -2.64$, $p < .05$). The degree of perception of the support received from the management team is therefore related to the degree of Turnover intention, Poor attendance and Poor Work Quality among participants.

Leadership Supervision and organizational disinvestment

The table 7 shows that participants achieved an average Leadership Supervision score ($M = 2.71$; $SD = 0.64$). They therefore often feel followed by the management team of their high school. On the relationship between Leadership Supervision and Organizational Disinvestment, the table ... show a negative correlation between Leadership Supervision and: Aggression $r(223) = -.149$, $p < .05$ and Misuse of information $r(223) = -.219$, $p < .01$. These findings mean that teachers who do not feel followed by their high school leadership are those who engage in aggressive behaviors at work and inappropriately use work-related information. Correlations with other dimensions of organizational disinvestment are not significant.

Table 7

Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix between Leadership Supervision and organizational disinvestment

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Turnover	3.86	0.76	---							
2. Aggression	0.72	0.84	-.147*	---						
3. Theft	0.81	0.70	-.316**	.859*	---					
4. Information Misuse	1.35	0.88	-.224**	.764*	.786*	---				
5. Resources Misuse	1.85	0.77	-.002	.802*	.769*	.805**	---			
6. Poor attendance	2.01	0.67	.245**	.501*	.391*	.438**	.561*	---		
7. Poor work quality	2.02	0.81	.325**	.358*	.293*	.259**	.469*	.567**	---	
8. Leadership Supervision	2.71	0.64	-.048	-.149*	-.051	-.219**	-.114	-.015	.017	--

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

The table 8 shows that Leadership Supervision predicts several organizational disinvestment dimensions, namely: Aggression $F(1,223) = 5.10$, $p < .05$; Misuse of information $F(1,223) = 11.3$, $p < .01$. Leadership Supervision explains respectively 2.2% and 4.8% each of those Organizational Disinvestment dimensions. A one-degree increase on Reduced Leadership Supervision: Aggression of 19.8% ($\beta = -.198$, $t(223) = -2.26$, $p < .05$) and Misuse of information 30.3% ($\beta = -.303$, $t(223) = -3.36$, $p < .01$).

Table 8

Simple linear regression between Leadership Supervision and organizational disinvestment

Dependant variables	Estimate (β)	T	R	R²	Adjuted R²	F
Aggression	-.198	-2.26*	.149	.022	.018	5.10*
Information Misuse	-.303	-3.36**	.219	.048	.044	11.3**

Note. Predictor = Leadership Supervision

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Overall, the results showed significant relationships between each of the dimensions of distributed leadership and different dimensions of organizational disinvestment. These results do not show which of the dimensions of distributed leadership best explains each of the dimensions of organizational disinvestment. A multiple linear regression was undertaken to achieve this. It appears that Participative Decision Making explains best: Turnover $\beta = -.549$; $t(220) = -3.83$, $p < .001$; Theft $\beta = -.683$; $t(220) = -4.02$, $p < .001$; Misuse Resources $\beta = -.493$; $t(220) = -2.57$, $p < .05$. Leadership supervision best explains Aggression $\beta = -.331$; $t(220) = -2.93$, $p < .01$ and Information Misuse $\beta = -.482$; $t(220) = -4.21$, $p < .001$. Leadership Support is the best predictor of Poor work quality $\beta = -.322$; $t(220) = -2.06$, $p < .05$. On the other hand, for Poor attendance, no significant result has been obtained.

Discussion and conclusion

The aim of this study was to study the relationship between Distributed Leadership in Government secondary school and Organizational Disinvestment of teachers. The results of this study reveal that the presence of distributed leadership is associated with a low degree of organizational disinvestment among teachers. This observation corroborates the research of Leithwood and Mascall (2008), which asserts that the active involvement of teachers in the decision-making process strengthens their sense of identification with the institution and their professional focus. Indeed, when educators feel heard, engaged, and appreciated in the pedagogical conduct of their institution, they are less likely to adopt behaviors of withdrawal, disengagement, or emotional detachment from their profession. Distributed leadership thus presents itself as a strategic tool for mobilizing educational teams.

According to the study's results, teachers who believe that their school is led by a cooperative leadership team – defined by group cohesion, team members with clear and unambiguous roles, and a common orientation towards goals – are more dedicated to their tasks. The study revealed that teachers' organizational disengagement is significantly affected by the level of support from the leadership team, which is consistent with previous findings (Nguni et al., 2006; Singh and Billingsley, 1998). Regarding the distribution of leadership responsibilities, our research showed that the formal distribution of supportive leadership within the leadership team significantly improved teachers' commitment to the school. Teachers who believe that support is evenly distributed within the leadership team are more likely to be engaged with the organization than those who believe that this support is concentrated on a single member.

Our results also confirm Spillane's (2006) research, which indicates that the sharing of responsibilities fosters a climate of trust, reduces organizational stress, and improves job satisfaction. However, certain poorly structured forms of distributed leadership, marked by a lack of clarity in roles or an overload of tasks, can conversely generate discomfort or latent disengagement. From a practical standpoint, school leaders would benefit from establishing clear, transparent, and equitable participatory governance mechanisms. Functional pedagogical councils, well-defined delegations, and spaces for teachers' expression can foster a culture of co-responsibility beneficial to the school dynamic.

Hulpia et al. (2012) find in their work that well-distributed leadership increases belonging and reduces disengagement. Barros Gavilanes (2017), who explores the correlation between the perception of shared leadership and teachers' intention to leave, shows that distributed and participative leadership significantly reduces the intention to leave. According to Tian et al. (2021), the support provided by the principal within an institution is the main factor encouraging teachers' participation in leadership. For him, any type of inclusion can significantly reduce disengagement. The work of Ma & Marion (2025) shows that distributed

leadership improves job satisfaction indirectly through well-being and motivation, two essential elements to prevent disengagement. MDPI (2023) in a systematic review highlights that distributed leadership increases teachers' satisfaction and engagement, fosters a positive professional climate, and limits their organizational disinvestment. Similarly, Frontiers (2025) highlights that in overly hierarchical environments, where teachers are rarely consulted, they feel disengaged. On the other hand, contexts that promote participation are associated with increased involvement. Nevertheless, this research has certain limitations. The exclusive use of self-reported questionnaires to measure both leadership and organizational disengagement could increase the risk of methodological bias, potentially responsible for certain correlations.

A mixed approach, incorporating for example peer evaluations or behavioural data (absenteeism, turnover), would minimize these biases. Studies on distributed leadership show that cultural variations (hierarchical distance, expectations regarding autonomy) have a strong impact. Our research, conducted in a Cameroonian context (collectivist), may not be generalizable to cultures with a stronger hierarchy, less favourable to the distribution of power. It is possible that other factors influence the leadership/disengagement link (digital infrastructures, organizational support, and climate of trust) but were not tested in the context of this thesis. The inclusion of indicators of these indicators would have enriched the analysis, similar to other studies on telework. Finally, our focus on exclusive disengagement did not allow for the examination of other effects of leadership, such as emotional engagement, team performance, or psychological well-being. Effects such as digital cognitive load, virtual stress, or communication fatigue were not taken into account.

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